

ISic0161

I.Sicily inscription 0161

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Tuuli Ahlholm,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance

Contr.Madonna della Catena

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico
Baldassare Romano, inventory 8ab

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. D(is) M(anibus)
2. L(ucius) Cor(nelius) Auctus
3. vix(it) an(nis) LXXX

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini

Absence of punctuation marks among words.

Bivona suggests the presence of a hedera leaf between D and M.

Translation (en)

To the Shades of the Underworld. Lucius Cornelius Auctus lived 80 years.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175697

EDR 077915

EDCS 8900393

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1980.0515

Bivona, L. 1994. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese. *Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica*. Palermo / Rome. At 82

Bivona, L 1975-1976. Nuove iscrizioni di Termini Imerese (Palermo). *Atti della Accademia di Scienze, Lettere a Arti di Palermo*. Ser.4, vol.35: 531-558. At 541 no.3 tav.2

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